

Volumetric Behaviour in Mixed Aqueous Solvents. Part-II. Partial Molal Volumes of Transfer of *N*-Methyl Tris(hydroxymethyl)glycine (Tricine) from Water to Aqueous Ethanol and Aqueous *t*-Butanol at 303.15 and 313.15 K

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The partial molal volume of *N*-methyl tris(hydroxymethyl)glycine (tricine) was determined at 303.15 and 313.15 K in aqueous solutions containing 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50% (w/w) (ethanol or *t*-butanol). Anomalous behaviour was observed in the region of structure enhancement of water by both the alcohols. In water-*t*-butanol, a negative deviation in the infinite dilution partial molal volume (\bar{V}_2^∞) was observed. In water-ethanol, a positive deviation near 10% (w/w) ethanol was followed by a large drop. Values for the infinite dilution partial molal expansibility (\bar{E}_2^∞) and the infinite dilution partial molal volume of transfer (\bar{V}_{tr}^∞) from water to the mixed solvents were obtained and their significance discussed.

A recent communication from this laboratory¹ dealt with the volumetric properties of tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (tris) in water and in mixed solvents containing varying compositions of water-ethanol and water-*t*-butanol. The infinite dilution partial molal volume (\bar{V}_2^∞) of tris was obtained in each solvent medium at 303.15 and 313.15 K. Furthermore, the infinite dilution partial molal volume of transfer of tris from water to each co-solvent (\bar{V}_{tr}^∞), defined by $\bar{V}_2^\infty(\text{cosolvent}) - \bar{V}_2^\infty(\text{water})$, was calculated. The \bar{V}_{tr}^∞ values exhibited maxima in the region of structure enhancement of water by ethanol and *t*-butanol. The inference was drawn that whereas tris promotes the structure of water, it disrupts the enhanced structure, probably through competition for H-bonds.

In continuation of this type of study, the behaviour of another biological buffer, *N*-methyl tris(hydroxymethyl)glycine (tricine) was selected for investigation in the same solvent media. This compound resembles tris in so far as they both contain the bulky hydrophilic group, $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_3$, but differs from it in one major respect: for whereas tris is effectively a neutral compound, tricine is an ampholyte that exists in the zwitterionic form. Hence electrostriction, virtually absent in tris solutions, is expected to play a major role in those containing tricine. This condition holds not only in water but also in aqueous alcohols, since amino acids are known to retain their zwitterionic character in alcohols². A comparison of the volumetric behaviour of tricine and tris could yield further insight into the nature of solute-solvent and solute-

solute interactions in mixed solvents, a subject that has received scant attention up to now³⁻⁶. Moreover, insight may be obtained on the relative effects of neutral and charged species on the stability of the enhanced water-ethanol and water-*t*-butanol structures.

Experimental

Details of the experimental procedure have already been presented¹. A commercial sample of tricine was recrystallised from 70% aqueous ethanol then dried under reduced pressure for ~48 h. Ethanol and *t*-butanol (AnalaR) were used as such. The concentration of tricine in water was varied within 0.01–0.5 *M*, but this range had to be gradually decreased as either alcohol was added, due to the diminished solubility of tricine in the alcohol rich media. Thus, in 50% (w/w) *t*-butanol, for example, measurements were made on solutions whose maximum tricine concentration was ca. 0.1 *M*. At least three independent sets of measurements were carried out at 303.15 and 313.15 K for each solvent composition.

Results and Discussion

Following the procedure outlined earlier¹, the results were fitted to the equation,

$$V = am^2 + bm + c \quad (1)$$

where V is the volume (cm^3) of solution containing 1000 g of the solvent, m is the molality of tricine

and a , b and c are constants. The constant a is an indicator of solute-solute interaction whereas b is numerically equivalent to the infinite dilution partial molal volume (\bar{V}_2^0) as well as the infinite dilution apparent molal volume (ϕ_2^0) and c is the volume (cm^3) of 1000 g of the mixed solvent. The experimental values of V and m were fitted to equation (1) by employing a computer regression analysis program from which the three constants were evaluated. In the 40 and 50% (w/w) alcohol media, however, due to the low solubility of tricine, the errors in measurement were magnified to an extent that made estimates of the values of the constant a somewhat unreliable. In these media, only b and c were of acceptable uncertainty. The infinite dilution partial molal expansibility (\bar{E}_2^0), defined by $\bar{E}_2^0 = d\bar{V}_2^0/dT$, was also obtained for each composition. The magnitude and sign of this term are of value in understanding structural interactions within the solution. Positive \bar{E}_2^0 values imply that the solution expands more rapidly than the solvent. Somewhat rarely, when the solvent expands faster, \bar{E}_2^0 is negative. The standard deviation in \bar{V}_2^0 , as obtained from the regression program, varied within 0.06–0.10 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for the 0–30% (w/w) alcohol solutions. For the 40 and 50% (w/w) solutions, however, the deviation was ca. 0.2 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$.

Table 1 lists values for a , b , c and \bar{E}_2^0 for tricine in the two types of media at 303.15 and 313.15 K. The value of b in pure water is 107.48 at 303.15 and 108.88 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 313.15 K. The small increase with temperature, reflected in the positive \bar{E}_2^0 value of 0.14 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$, is normal. The relatively rapid expansion of the solution, as compared to the solvent, is presumably due to the release of water bound in secondary solvation shells upon raising

the temperature. Since bound water occupies less volume than bulk water, b should rise with temperature⁷. The infinite dilution partial molal volume of an electrolyte (\bar{V}_2^0) may be written as the sum of intrinsic and electrostriction terms⁸,

$$\bar{V}_2^0 = \bar{V}_2^0(\text{int}) + \bar{V}_2^0(\text{elect}) \quad (2)$$

The intrinsic component for tricine may be estimated from group contributions in related compounds. The \bar{V}_2^0 values for the α -amino acids glycine⁸ and serine⁸ in water at 298.15 K are 43.19 and 16.02 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively, from which it may be concluded that replacement of H– by $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ causes an increase in \bar{V}_2^0 by 17.83 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$. Secondly, following the procedure of Millero *et al.*⁸, \bar{V}_2^0 for lactamide, a neutral isomer of alanine, is estimated by adding the \bar{V}_2^0 values of glycolamide⁹ and alanine then subtracting that of glycine. This procedure yields a value of 72.57 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$. $\bar{V}_2^0(\text{int})$ for tricine, which may be viewed as the sum of \bar{V}_2^0 of lactamide and the effect of three replacements of H– by $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$, is thus seen to have the value of 127.06 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K. When this is compared with the value of 106.78 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for tricine at the same temperature (estimated from the experimental quantity at 303.15 K (using $\bar{E}_2^0 = 0.14 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)), $\bar{V}_2^0(\text{elect})$ is found to be $-20.28 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$. This effect is somewhat larger than ΔV for the reaction, $\text{RCOOH} + \text{RNH}_2 \rightarrow \text{RCOO}^- + \text{RNH}_3^+$, reported¹⁰ to have values in the range -13 to $-17 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$. The higher than expected electrostriction may arise from the additivity assumptions, but may also be due to overlap of the hydration co-spheres of the ionic groups with that of $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_3$. An alternative explanation is the formation of cooperative H-bonds between $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_3$ and the ionic group.

TABLE 1—VALUES FOR CONSTANTS a , b AND c OF EQUATION (1) AND \bar{E}_2^0 FOR TRICINE IN WATER-ETHANOL AND WATER-t-BUTANOL AS A FUNCTION OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION*

In water-ethanol (ethanol %, w/w)						
	0	10	20	30	40	50
a	7.96 11.86	-1.5 -1.3	23.89 18.1	25.22 22.68	— —	— —
b	107.48 108.88	113.94 115.6	108.14 109.74	101.04 104.38	111.24 109.72	110.69 112.05
c	1004.37 1007.84	1020.19 1025.07	1035.86 1043.58	1053.81 1082.78	1075.9 1084.3	1103.043 1112.923
\bar{E}_2^0	0.14	0.166	0.16	0.334	-0.152	0.136
In water-t-butanol (t-butanol %, w/w)						
	0	10	20	30	40	50
a	7.96 11.86	37.4 25.35	61.5 50.5	85.68 65.7	— —	— —
b	107.48 108.88	100.66 103.58	100.85 102.37	100.17 100.92	108.25 109.35	108.96 109.26
c	1004.37 1007.84	1019.69 1024.19	1037.01 1043.67	1064.9 1069.23	1088.91 1096.86	1116.27 1126.89
\bar{E}_2^0	0.14	0.292	0.152	0.075	0.11	0.03

*In each row, the first set of values is at 303.15 K and the second is at 313.15 K; Units: volume, $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$; expansibility, $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$.

Further inspection of Table 1 reveals an increasing trend in the values of the solute-solute interaction coefficient (a) with higher alcohol content, the effect being much more pronounced with t-butanol than with ethanol, indicating that electrostriction is diminished at the higher tricine concentrations. Such behaviour is common to solutions of electrolytes in water¹¹. Its magnitude, however, particularly in t-butanol rich solutions, is quite considerable. For example, at 303.15 K, the partial molal volume for a 0.1 M tricine solution ($\bar{V}_{0.1}$) in 30% (w/w) aqueous t-butanol (as calculated from $\bar{V}_2 = \bar{V}_2^0 + 2am$) is 117.31 cm³ mol⁻¹. This is far in excess of the infinite dilution value of 100.17 cm³ mol⁻¹, but still much lower than the estimated (see above) intrinsic value of 126.63 cm³ mol⁻¹. This computation suggests that the extent of electrostriction for 0.1 M tricine in this medium is roughly half that in an infinitely dilute solution. On the other hand, the value of $\bar{V}_{0.1}$ in 30% (w/w) ethanol, calculated from data in Table 1, is 106.08 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 303.15 K. When this is compared with the infinite dilution value of 101.04 cm³ mol⁻¹, the increase, although quite pronounced in its own right, is much less than that observed with t-butanol. Thus, the presence of the bulky hydrophobic group in t-butanol significantly augments the electrostatic type of solute-solute interactions in tricine. Furthermore, with the sole exception of the value in pure water, Table 1 shows that the extent of solute-solute interaction varies inversely with temperature, in tune with the expectation that ionic interactions are weakened at higher temperatures. The marked sensitivity of the constant a to concentration of tricine is in sharp contrast to the low sensitivity exhibited by tris¹, where small negative and positive values were reported for most solvent compositions. For example, at 303.15 K, the values of a for tris were found to be only 4.2 and -2.2 in 30% (w/w) ethanol and 30% t-butanol, respectively. This behaviour suggests that the ionic character of tricine and the nature of the co-solvent predominant in influencing the concentration dependence of its partial molal volume.

Fig. 1 gives plots, at 303.15 and 313.15 K, of the infinite dilution partial molal volume of transfer of tricine from water to aqueous ethanol and aqueous t-butanol as a function of solvent composition. A maximum in \bar{V}_{tr}^0 is present in the vicinity of 10% (w/w) ethanol, followed by a minimum at 30%. It is noteworthy that this maximum is located within the region of structure enhancement of water by ethanol, which spans the composition interval 9–18% (w/w) ethanol at 303.15 K¹². The behaviour of tricine in 10% (w/w) ethanol resembles that of tris¹ and may be similarly interpreted by postulating that tricine acts to promote the structure of water but has a disruptive influence on that of ethanol-water. Such behaviour may be attributed to competition for H-bonds which may lead to a collapse of the highly ordered cage-like structure of water-ethanol. By contrast, in 30% (w/w) ethanol, tricine is most electrostricted and the structure promotion

Fig. 1. Infinite dilution partial molal volumes of transfer of tricine from water to (1a) aqueous ethanol and (1b) aqueous t-butanol as a function of alcohol content: (—) 303.15 and (---) 313.15 K.

is maximised. The presence of a maximum and a minimum in \bar{V}_{tr}^0 suggests at least two competing influences. The first is a disruption by tricine of the ordered structure of water-ethanol. The second involves the three components in a mutual, cooperative type of interaction, presumably including low energy cage-like structures of tricine with the two solvent components. The first influence may involve the overlap of the two hydrophilic hydration spheres of tricine and ethanol, squeezing out some bound water molecules and causing a net decrease of the extent of H-bonding in water⁶.

Fig. 1 also reveals a broad though in the region of structure enhancement of water by t-butanol. At 298 K, this region extends from nearly pure water up to ca. 30% (w/w) t-butanol, with the maximum effect located in the vicinity of 14% (w/w) alcohol⁶. Thus, unlike its behaviour in 10% (w/w) ethanol, tricine may be said to exert a net stabilising influence on the enhanced water-t-butanol structure throughout the entire enhancement region. This suggests, in the present case, the dominance of the cooperative over the disruptive type of interaction. Thus, it

may be also postulated that, in contrast to the water-ethanol case, there is significantly less overlap, this time between the hydrophobic hydration co-sphere of t-butanol and the hydrophilic one of tricine.

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